

Procrastination's Definition and its Medication

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ABSTRACT

This article aims to take a deep dive into the basics and the why of procrastination and provide solutions as to what can be done to combat this behaviour. First of all, mechanisms of procrastination are described. Next, some solutions to the problem are discussed and their example implementation.

1 Introduction

Academic procrastination is the intentional delay in the beginning of important academic activities which is highly common in students [1]. Many students have experienced this phenomenon, but why?

1.1 The Why

It is commonly accepted that procrastination is a voluntary but irrational delay of intended course of actions, in other words, the avoidance of the implementation of an intention. Kyung Ryung Kim et al. [2] concluded from a meta-analysis that there is a negative correlation between procrastination and academic performance and this seems logical that if a student delays studying for an exam up until 2 days before, they might not have time to cover all the material that they will be tested on.

1.2 Role of Self-Regulation

Rebetez MML et al. [3] concluded procrastination as a result of self regulation failure. In their study, they found a positive correlation between high impulsivity and procrastination. If a student sees a text message notification (the distraction) and immediately starts to attend to it (high impulsivity) this will lead to the student being less productive overall and find it difficult to re-enter the flow state. Flow is defined as an experiential state that occurs during full capacity engagement in which an individual is performing to the best of their ability and meeting the demands of the task they are focusing on [4]. This phenomenon can also be termed 'Hyperfocus' [5]. After checking the

notification and switching back to studying can have an adverse effect known as 'Attention Residue' [6]. This phenomenon makes it much more difficult to go into the flow state again making the person less productive, efficient and bored and ultimately leading to wasting time and procrastination.

1.3 Intrusive Thoughts and Daydreaming

Rebetez MML et al. also described a positive correlation between intrusive thoughts and procrastination [3]. Daydreaming was identified as a major distraction in the results. If a student is reading a relatively less interesting subject, they are more likely to dose off into intrusive thoughts. This is a major distraction and distracts the person from going into the flow state. This is known as maladaptive daydreaming which has also been termed a behavioral addiction [7].

1.4 The role of internet

The internet does not even help as well. The internet is an essential tool for students in the 21st century but overuse of the internet can have negative consequences for students and may lead to academic procrastination and worse, Internet Addiction [8]. Hayat AA et al. concluded that there was a positive correlation between academic procrastination and internet addiction. This is one of the most common reasons of procrastination in students.

1.5 Molecular and Neural Basis

Zhang et al. have also tried to find molecular and neural causes for procrastination [9]. Their

research focusing on finding the molecular and structural basis in the brain for procrastination have led them to highlight the temporal decision model theory. The theory tries to combine the previously identified causes of procrastination: the motivation to avoid, the motivation to act and the time preference effect. They found that people move the tasks to later dates (task aversiveness) which leads to the task moving closer to the deadlines (increasing the motivation to act) but this act is the basis of procrastination. At the neural level, things remain unclear but it is possible that the parahippocampal region is involved in the postponement of tasks working against the hippocampus which schedules the tasks and works in their completion right now.

2 Suggested Solutions to Test

2.1 Intentions

Owens et al. found people who rated themselves as highly likely to procrastinate did indeed fail most of the time to keep their appointments [10]. To combat this, the researchers devised a simple hypothesis: if the students clearly made and stated the intention of completing a task or coming to an appointment, would the students still procrastinate? The answer was that students who clearly made the intention were nearly 8 times more likely to complete their work. This was proven statistically and there was an improvement in the procrastinative behaviour of the students who classified themselves as high procrastinators.

2.2 Parkinson's Law

This law states: "Work expands so as to fill the time available for its completion" which was first conceived of by C. Northcote Parkinson in a 1955 article in *The Economist* [11]. This is a profound law and tries to explain procrastination when a person is seemingly busy. The fact is that if more than required time is available for a task's completion, it is highly likely that a person would perform less efficiently to fill the time. This is subconscious and can be explained with a simple, very often occurring situation. Suppose a student has a deadline to submit an article in a month or a researcher has to submit a paper for peer review;

it is very likely that they would use up all the time to submit the paper. On the other hand, if that same paper is to be submitted in one week, it is likely that they will submit the paper on time.

2.3 Deadlines

Deadlines are a great way to optimize and pick out tasks that have more importance and are due soon. Stephen B. Hanauer stated that an individual's performance on a task is related to their stress level by a bell-shaped curve [12]. Humans tend to perform best in the middle when there is moderate stress as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Showing the Yerkes-Dodson Effect [13]

3 Methods for Testing

The question now arises, how do we devise a solution to all of the problems that have been identified. A simple solution exists to merge all of the solutions mentioned in section 3: calendars. They are a great way to manage time, see a summary of the whole day at a glance and set deadlines on when to work on a project and how long to work on it. For choosing which tasks to put in a calendar, see 'Time Management and Task Prioritization' article [14].

A student of medicine was the test subject trying out an example routine taking into consideration the points mentioned in section 3. A schedule planned for the whole day is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Showing the student's schedule of a day.

This is just an example but it clearly shows how the student planned their day. It allocates blocks of time to the most important tasks and takes into consideration existing responsibilities. Existing responsibilities are compulsory tasks that cannot be delegated, are binding and mostly have been tasked by someone senior than the subject in question [14]. Existing responsibilities were the Anatomy and Histology Practicals at the University as well as the Molecular Mechanisms of disease Lecture. The calendar shows clearly when a specific task should be started and how long should it be worked on as well as what to do during the day.

The calendar clearly shows the intention of the student to study a particular subject at a given time (clear intention), it fixes how long the student can work on the task (minimizing the effect of Parkinson's Law) and sets clear deadlines for the completion of the task to work on the next task. This also minimizes time wasting by removing the need to find out what to do next [14].

The student reported much greater motivation to complete the tasks, actually being able to complete the tasks and just generally reporting much lower feelings of being lost about what to do. The time scheduling in a calendar is not very difficult and has a great upside.

4 Discussion

This study was not as extensive so as to allow generalization of these findings to the general student population but it does suggest that the time scheduling technique here works. Further research should focus on replicating the effects in a larger student population and separating them into two groups in which only one uses this calendar technique.

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